

Assessing Regional Coordination Mechanisms within the LAPSSSET Infrastructural Initiative for Economic Security Stabilization in the Horn of Africa

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ABSTRACT

Keywords:

LAPSSSET, Regional Coordination Mechanism (RCM), Horn of Africa (HoA), Economic Security Stabilization and Infrastructure Development

Located in the Horn of Africa, the Lamu Port South Sudan Ethiopia Transport (LAPSSSET) infrastructural initiative was conceived in 1975 as a strategic resource for spurring economic growth and stabilization of a region historically riddled by both ecological fragility and ideological conflict. However, for several decades the initiative remained lull, until 2012, when it was revamped with the mandate of: decongesting the port of Mombasa and the Northern Transport Corridor in Kenya; and spurring regional integration between Kenya, South Sudan and Ethiopia, through infrastructure development and trade. From the lenses of regionalism, the LAPSSSET infrastructural initiative was conceptualized as a narrow plan, aimed at integrating only the tripartite states of Kenya, Ethiopia and South Sudan, as opposed to a multifaceted approach for integrating the greater Horn of Africa - a geostrategic region plagued with infrastructure deficits, violent conflicts, humanitarian crises, economic shocks and instabilities. This study specifically explored the role of the LAPSSSET regional coordination mechanism (RCM) in bolstering economic security stabilization in the Horn of Africa. The research adopted a descriptive design, targeting; six Kenyan county governments traversed by the LAPSSSET initiative, eight key national government LAPSSSET stakeholder institutions, and one international organization. Data was collected through; the questionnaire - administered to 56 technical respondents, and moderated focus group discussions with the border communities of Moyale and Lodwar sub-counties, the Kenyan border towns with Ethiopia and South Sudan, respectively. The questionnaire was pilot-tested to ensure reliability and clarity, and data were analyzed using inferential and descriptive statistical techniques, specifically multiple regression analysis. The study was guided by the theories of regionalism and complex interdependence, within a conceptual framework aimed at generating insights pertinent to regional economic stabilization. Findings indicated that the LAPSSSET RCM has a significant positive influence on regional economic stabilization ($B = 0.476$, $p < 0.000$), highlighting the critical need for its formal operationalization, governance strengthening, and community inclusion. The study concluded that a functional and inclusive RCM is pivotal for realizing the transformative economic interdependence, regional integration and stability potentials of the LAPSSSET in the greater Horn of Africa. Policy recommendations include; formalizing the LAPSSSET RCM, establishing a LAPSSSET supranational umbrella institution for bolstered member state governance collaboration, establishment and development of the LAPSSSET transnational special economic zone areas (TSEZAs), and expansion of the LAPSSSET mandate, and thus, inclusion of the other IGAD states into the initiative.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

The Horn of Africa - located on the easternmost part of the African mainland and comprising of Somalia (including the de facto independent Somaliland), Ethiopia, Djibouti, Eritrea, Kenya, Sudan, and South Sudan - is one of the most unstable and conflict-ridden regions globally, owing to its geostrategic importance to; the African and global economy, security and trade – especially because Eritrea, Djibouti and Somalia are located at the entrance of the red sea, which is one of the most crowded maritime coasts with several harbors and ports that bridge the Indian and Arabian peninsulas (Asefa, 2003). The region is also a pivotal space for power struggles between the West and East. On one hand, the west led by the United States of America (USA) have established military bases in Kenya (at Manda bay in Lamu county) and Djibouti (camp Lemonnier) - ostensibly for security surveillance – while on the other, the region forms a strategic corridor for the Chinese Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) infrastructural connectivity project (Wang et al., 2022). In this context, economic collaboration is fronted as the pathway for growth and stability (Belhaj, 2024). Terese and Tesfaye (2023) have linked the militarization of the Horn of Africa - by competing global and regional powers - to the exchange for economic trickles to the friendly host regimes. Despite these economic and military capitals, the region is replete with intermittent armed violence and insurgencies, mainly by non-state actors - such as; ethnic rebel groups, self-defense militias and transnational organizations affiliated with Al-Qaeda and Islamic State (IS) - who challenge the legitimacy of such friendly host regimes.

The persistent human security crisis in the Horn of Africa is a symptom of underlying fragility in the region (Pillai and Corral, 2022). The humanitarian crises in Ethiopia, the military coups in the Sudan, attacks on civilian populations by armed groups, and the protracted cross-border political tensions and security challenges, are some of the issues linked to complex historical legacies. Ultimately, the region's susceptibility to armed conflicts and insurgencies recreates the region into economic shocks and

instabilities. It was against this background that regional leaders from South Sudan, Ethiopia and Kenya established the Lamu Port South Sudan Ethiopia Transport (LAPSSET) infrastructural initiative in-order to: decongest the northern corridor in Kenya; and spur regional integration between the tripartite states, through infrastructure development and trade (LAPSSET Corridor Development Authority Strategic Plan, 2023-2027).

As a strategy for spurring economic integration among the tripartite states, and thus, re-positioning the Horn of Africa as a competitive logistics and trade hub, the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative has seen the completion of its initial three deep-sea berths (each with a quay length of 400 meters, and depths of minus 18 meters) of the new Lamu port, and commenced construction and operationalization of the initiatives' transnational highways. This is intended to seamlessly interconnect the LAPSSET tripartite states, and thus, ease the movement of people and cargo between the new port of Lamu, and Ethiopia - through Garissa, Isiolo and Moyale Counties - and to South Sudan – through Isiolo and Turkana Counties. Beyond its economic ambitions, LAPSSET was envisaged as a strategic instrument for regional cooperation, offering a land bridge across Eastern Africa and extending connectivity toward Central and West Africa (Brief on LAPSSET Corridor Project, 2016).

Notwithstanding its transformative potential, the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative faces significant political, institutional, and security challenges that threatens its capacity to deliver inclusive stabilization outcomes. These challenges include; inadequate financing, fluctuating political commitment among partner states, protracted political instabilities in some of the cooperating states, weak coordination frameworks, competing national priorities, and persistent insecurity along the LAPSSET corridor (AUDA-NEPAD, 2022). Social contracting risks and structural inequalities have also emerged, particularly among historically marginalized and conflict-prone communities in northern Kenya, where competition over land, natural resources, and extractive discoveries intersected with the proliferation of small arms and

porous borders (Mtuku, 2021). While infrastructure has increasingly been adopted globally as a stabilization tool in fragile and conflict-affected settings, empirical evidences have suggested that physical assets alone were insufficient to secure durable peace and economic security (Brown, 2005; Thacker et al., 2018). Empirical experiences from comparable corridor initiatives have demonstrated that coordinated institutional frameworks, inclusive governance mechanisms, and cross-border policy harmonization are critical for translating infrastructure investments into sustained economic and security dividends (Naz et al., 2022; Balbaa et al., 2023). Against this backdrop, this study assessed the effectiveness of regional coordination mechanisms within the LAPSSSET infrastructural initiative, as a model for economic security stabilization in the Horn of Africa. By interrogating the limitations of a narrow physical-infrastructure approach and emphasizing the role of coordination, governance, and regional institutions, the study contributes empirical evidence to policy debates on infrastructure-led stabilization in Africa, and thus, bolsters the broader aspirations of the African Union's Vision 2063 on continental integration, security and peace, and inclusive economic and social development.

Statement of the Problem

While the LAPSSSET infrastructural initiative has made notable progress towards integrating the tripartite states of Kenya, South Sudan and Ethiopia - through infrastructure development and trade – a critical review of institutional reports and scholarly literature about the LAPSSSET revealed that the initiatives' existing mandate is mired by conceptual design obscurities, which implicates its implementation among the cooperating states in the Horn of Africa region. The initiatives' existing mandate was initially conceptualized by South Sudan, Ethiopia and Kenya (LAPSSSET Corridor Development Authority Strategic Plan, 2023-2027), and thus, the existing mandate may have overlooked the Horn of Africa's broader need for peace and security, as well as the regions' wholesome economic security stabilization effect, which may

accrue from a mega transnational infrastructure in the caliber of the LAPSSSET infrastructural initiative. From the lenses of regionalism, the LAPSSSET infrastructural initiative may have been conceptualized as a narrow plan, aimed at integrating only the tripartite states of Kenya, Ethiopia and South Sudan, as opposed to a multifaceted approach for integrating the greater Horn of Africa - a geostrategic region plagued with infrastructure deficits, violent armed conflicts, humanitarian crises, economic shocks and instabilities.

Moreover, the LAPSSSET initiative was largely conceived as a physical infrastructure project, with insufficient integration of regional governance, institutional coordination, and security frameworks. Despite the mandates of regional bodies such as the Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD) and the Horn of Africa Initiative (HoAI) to promote coordinated regional integration, peace, and economic cooperation, there was limited empirical evidence linking LAPSSSET's conceptualization and implementation to these institutional mechanisms. Given the empirical evidences that well-designed and coordinated transport corridors significantly contribute to regional economic growth and stability, the absence of a clearly articulated regional coordination mechanism within LAPSSSET constituted a critical knowledge and policy gap.

In the foregoing design related ambiguities – as currently adopted by the tripartite states - this study assessed the viability of the LAPSSSET infrastructural initiative as an economic security stabilization frontier in the Horn of Africa, focusing on its; conceptual design, economic security imperatives and regional coordination mechanism, with the objective of evaluating whether the LAPSSSET infrastructural initiative provides for a common understanding of what collective regional cooperation entails.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Review

This study was anchored on the theories of regionalism and complex interdependence, which

together provided a coherent analytical framework for assessing the viability of the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative as an economic security stabilization frontier in the Horn of Africa. These theories guided the examination of the initiative's conceptual design, its regional coordination mechanisms, and its economic security imperatives within a region characterized by fragility, interdependence, and geopolitical competition.

The theory of regionalism was advanced by Joseph Nye (1968), who described an international region as a finite group of geographically proximate states bound by mutual interdependence. Nye (1968) defined regionalism as the formation of interstate groupings aimed at advancing shared political, economic, and security interests. Ethier (1998) expanded this perspective by describing regional cooperation as the expression of a common identity and purpose, operationalized through institutions that shape collective state action. Ethier (1998) observed that regionalism gained prominence in the post-Second World War and Cold War periods, as states increasingly sought collective mechanisms to enhance political influence, regional stability, and economic resilience. These arguments were particularly relevant to the Horn of Africa, where states face shared challenges of underdevelopment, insecurity, and marginalization from global trade networks.

Schimmelfennig (2018) further contributed to regional integration theory by highlighting intergovernmentalism and neofunctionalism as key explanatory frameworks. Under intergovernmentalism, national governments were regarded as the primary actors in integration processes, delegating authority to regional institutions in-order to secure national interests while retaining ultimate control. Söderbaum (2011) similarly emphasized the centrality of states and domestic political considerations in shaping regional integration outcomes. Conversely, neofunctionalism emphasized the role of supranational institutions and non-state actors, particularly regional secretariats, in deepening integration beyond initial intergovernmental agreements. Together, these perspectives underscored the importance of

institutional design, political commitment, and governance mechanisms in sustaining regional initiatives such as the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative.

Christian et al. (2022) linked the resurgence of regionalism to increased global interconnectedness, arguing that states were compelled to cooperate regionally in-order to address shared challenges. They distinguished between security, political, and economic regionalism, with economic regionalism focusing on trade blocs and infrastructure corridors designed to enhance economic integration and growth. Börzel and Risse (2013) further observed regional cooperation as the joint exercise of political authority through intergovernmental institutions, in-order to resolve collective action problems related to economic, political, and security issues. Within the context of the Horn of Africa, the Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD) functions as both a regional economic community (REC) and a regional security complex (RSC), with the mandate of promoting peace, security, and sustainable development through coordinated regional action (IGAD, 2024). The theory of regionalism, therefore, provided a useful lens for assessing whether LAPSSET's conceptual design and coordination mechanisms aligned with regional integration frameworks.

To complement regionalism, the study applied complex interdependence theory, as articulated by Keohane and Nye (2000). According to Keohane and Nye (2000), complex interdependence theory - in the context of international political economy (IPE) - describes the emerging nature of the global political economy, where relations between countries are observed as having become increasingly complex and deep. From the lenses of liberalism, complex interdependence theory champions for the use of global institutions - like the World Bank Group (WBG) and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) - and regional economic communities (RECs) - like the European Union and African Union, in-order to inspire cooperation for similar aspirations, and thus, a peaceful world or regional order among cooperating states, as long as there are mutual gains. Braddon (2012) demonstrated

that economic interdependence played a significant role in both the emergence and resolution of conflicts in Africa, arguing that trade, investment, and shared infrastructure reduced incentives for violent confrontation. Despite extensive application of these theories in European integration studies, their application to Africa's mega infrastructural initiatives remained limited. Consequently, the combined use of regionalism and complex interdependence was critical for evaluating LAPSSET's potential contribution to economic security stabilization in the Horn of Africa.

Regional Coordination Mechanism for the LAPSSET Infrastructural Initiative

Empirical literature on the regional coordination mechanisms underpinning the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative remained limited, reflecting a broader scholarly gap in Africa's transnational infrastructure corridors. Nonetheless, existing studies on regional integration, infrastructure-led development, and conflict mitigation provided relevant insights into the potential role of coordinated infrastructure projects in fragile regions. Adar (2011) observed that regional integration was instrumental in fostering peace and stability, noting that shared infrastructure initiatives enhanced diplomatic relations and cooperation among participating states. In this context, LAPSSET was widely viewed as a mechanism for strengthening cooperation among Kenya, Ethiopia, and South Sudan through shared economic interests.

Stewart (2008) provided empirical evidence that inter-regional infrastructure projects promoted social cohesion by improving access to resources and essential services for marginalized communities. According to Stewart, improved access to education, healthcare, and markets reduced grievances and mitigated the risk of violent conflict. These findings were particularly relevant to communities residing along the LAPSSET transect, which have historically experienced marginalization, underdevelopment, and recurrent insecurity. Stewart (2008) further emphasized that inclusive planning and community participation during project implementation were

critical for minimizing social tensions and enhancing local ownership of infrastructure initiatives.

From a liberal stand-point, infrastructure-led cooperation was also associated with reduced interstate conflict through increased economic interdependence. Braddon (2012) demonstrated that regions with strong economic linkages experienced lower propensities for conflict, as the costs of violence increasingly outweighed potential gains. Similarly, Naz et al., (2022) observed that the China–Pakistan Economic Corridor generated positive spillovers in trade, employment, and social development, reinforcing the stabilizing effects of coordinated infrastructure investments. Additionally, Balbaa et al., (2023), in their assessment of the Trans-Africa Highway Network, observed that reductions in transport time and border procedures significantly enhanced trade flows and economic growth across participating countries.

Despite these empirical insights, studies explicitly linking the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative to established regional coordination frameworks such as Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD) and the Horn of Africa Initiative (HoAI) remained scarce. The HoAI, established in 2019, emphasized coordinated regional action through economic and transport corridors as a strategy for addressing shared development challenges (HoAI Communique, 2024). However, despite the significant milestones made by the LAPSSET initiative since 2012, the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative had not been formally prioritized within HoAI's active corridor portfolio, raising questions regarding institutional alignment and regional ownership. This disconnect suggested that LAPSSET's potential contribution to regional economic security and stabilization had not been fully leveraged by cooperating states in the Horn of Africa. Consequently, the absence of empirical evidence on LAPSSET's regional coordination mechanisms constituted a critical research gap. This study therefore examined the extent to which LAPSSET's coordination arrangements supported regional cooperation and economic security stabilization in the Horn of Africa.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A descriptive research design was adopted to capture stakeholder perspectives and assess the influence of the LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism on the economic security stabilization of the Horn of Africa. This complemented the aspirations of Kombo and Orodho (2002), who asserted that descriptive research design was suitable for collecting data and information about people's attitudes, habits, opinions, or any of the variety of social issues. This design, therefore, allowed the researcher to obtain detailed insights into how the LAPSSET regional coordination structures, processes, and interactions contribute to stabilizing economic security across the Horn of Africa, while maintaining the feasibility of data collection within the context of the tripartite states of Kenya, Ethiopia, and South Sudan,

Study Site and Units of Analysis

The study was conducted within the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative, which spans Kenya, Ethiopia, and South Sudan, focusing on the six Kenyan counties traversed by the initiative, namely; Turkana, Samburu, Isiolo, Marsabit, Garissa, and Lamu (Rift Valley Institute, 2016). These counties were selected owing to their direct involvement in and exposure to the activities of the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative. The units of analysis included four main stakeholder groups. First, the key national government stakeholder institutions responsible for coordinating and implementing the LAPSSET initiative in Kenya, such as the; LAPSSET Corridor Development Authority (LCDA), Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure, the National Treasury & Economic Planning, and the New Partnership for African Development – African Peer Review Mechanism (NEPAD-APRM). Second, county governments traversed by the LAPSSET initiative in Kenya, whose officials facilitate local implementation and policy alignment. Third, the border communities in Moyale and Lodwar sub-counties, the border towns between Kenya and Ethiopia and Kenya and South-Sudan, respectively, and who are directly affected by cross-border

infrastructure. Fourth, an international organization in Kenya, with insights about the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative. Collectively, these units provided insights into the design, implementation, and effectiveness of regional coordination mechanisms within the LAPSSET initiative.

Target Population and Sample Size

The study population comprised the key stakeholders directly engaged in regional coordination mechanisms within the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative. This included: national government officials responsible for policy formulation, planning, and operational oversight; county government officials along the LAPSSET transect in Kenya, tasked with local implementation; and border community members affected by cross-border infrastructure projects, and one international organization with insights about the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative. To ensure representative inclusion across these groups, stratified sampling was applied, followed by simple random selection within each stratum (Tyrell & Hunt, 2001; Kanupriya, 2012). Using Yamane's (1967) formula at a 95% confidence level and 10% margin of error, the national government sample comprised 29 respondents, while county governments comprised of 25 respondents, and the international organization comprised of 2 respondents, yielding a total of 56 technical respondents. Additionally, two focus group discussions (FGDs) involving 20 community discussants (10 each at Moyale and Lodwar) formed part of the sample size.

Data Collection, Pilot Testing, and Instrument Reliability and Validity

A mixed-methods approach was employed to collect data on regional coordination mechanisms within the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative. Structured questionnaires captured quantitative data from national government and county government officials, focusing on intergovernmental communication, joint decision-making, and collaborative implementation processes. Focus group discussions (FGDs) were moderated in Moyale and Lodwar sub-counties, and gathered qualitative insights from the border communities

regarding cross-border coordination. (Gillham, 2013; Krueger, 1994).

Pilot testing involved six technical officers from LAPSSET Corridor Development Authority, approximately 10% of the sample, who assessed the clarity, appropriateness, and comprehension of the questionnaire items. Feedback from the pilot test led to minor revisions that improved the flow and readability of the instrument (Babbie, 2016; Creswell, 2014).

Reliability of the questionnaire was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.773 for RCM, above the 0.70 threshold, indicating strong internal consistency (Harris & Green, 2022). Validity was evaluated through content, face, and construct measures. Experts reviewed the instrument for relevance, while pilot participants confirmed question clarity and appropriateness (Chen & Yao, 2023; Kamau & Owusu, 2021). Construct validity was further supported by a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of 0.773 and a significant Bartlett's Test of Sphericity ($p < 0.000$), confirming adequacy for factor analysis and strong construct validity (Patel & Njoroge, 2020).

Data Analysis

Data were cleaned, coded, and analyzed using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS v26). Descriptive statistics summarized respondent profiles, while **linear regression** tested the influence of the LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism on the economic security stabilization of the Horn of Africa, and thus, the regression formula:

$$ESS_{HoA} = \beta_0 + \beta_3 RCM + e$$

Where; β_0 represented the Y-Intercept, β_3 was the regression co-efficient representing the process, **RCM** represented the regional coordination mechanisms for the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative, and e was the error term.

5.0 RESULTS

Descriptive Analysis for Regional Coordination Mechanism of the LAPSSET Infrastructural Initiative

The study explored the regional coordination mechanism of the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative, aimed at regional economic stabilization of the Horn of Africa. Respondents indicated their level of agreement with statements relating to three main indicators: existence and operationalization of regional coordination mechanisms, stakeholder engagement and community inclusion, and regional integration & economic interdependence. Responses were rated on a five-point Likert scale and the results are summarized in the Table 1 (See Appendix 1).

According to the findings, the existence and functioning of a regional coordination mechanism under the LAPSSET initiative is actually quite weak. A mere 14.6% of respondents agreed that the mechanism exists and is ratified by Kenya, Ethiopia, and South Sudan, while 47.9% disagreed and 31.3% were neutral, and thus, giving the statement a mean equal to 2.29 and standard deviation equal to 0.94. Likewise, whereas 14.6% agreed that the LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism is operational and that it benefits from committed governance support, 50% disagreed and 27.1% were neutral ($M = 2.19$, $SD = 0.96$). Additionally, only 14.6% of respondents agreed that a joint regional body has been established to manage the LAPSSET related activities, with 50% disagreeing and 29.2% neutral ($M = 2.23$, $SD = 0.93$).

In terms of formalization, the principles around a regional coordination mechanism for the LAPSSET do not appear to have been established. Therefore, operationalization of such a mechanism in practice is not adequate, and thus, there are governance and institutional gaps which limit cross-border coordination and strategy alignment. The results also showed that there was moderate, but inconsistent, stakeholder engagement and community inclusion in the LAPSSET initiative. According to these findings, 39.6% of respondents strongly agreed while 14.6% agreed that there is meaningful involvement of the surrounding local communities in the initiation and planning of LAPSSET projects. On the contrary,

31.3% disagreed while 14.6% were neutral on this issue (M = 3.77, SD = 1.13).

A LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism has potentials for ensuring equitable access to economic integration benefits among affected communities in the Horn of Africa region, as the respondents strongly agreed (37.5%) and agreed (50%) (Mean = 4.25; SD = 0.66). Additionally, all participants (100%) either strongly agree (58.3%) or agree (41.7%) that a LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism has potentials for enhancing collaboration among governments, private sector and civil society of the greater Horn of Africa (M = 4.58, SD = 0.50).

With regard to regional integration and economic interdependence, the outcomes were mostly positive. Almost all respondents (93.8%) either agreed (31.3% agreed and 62.5% strongly agreed) that a LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism can strengthen political and economic relations between cooperating states (M=4.56, SD=0.59). Similarly, there was agreement (M = 4.25, SD = 0.57) that the regional coordination mechanism should not be exclusive to East Africa, but should facilitate the participation of other cooperating states in the Horn of Africa region, like; Uganda, Eritrea, the Sudan, Somalia and Djibouti. Furthermore, 93.8% of respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that governance support from regional institutions such as; the economic cooperation and regional integration division of the Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD); and the Horn of Africa Initiative (HoAI), should be given to the

LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism, in-order to enhance investors’ confidence (M = 4.21, SD = 0.54). The findings show that there is a strong view that a LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism may foster regional integration and interdependence in the greater Horn of Africa.

The results showed that a LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism was not in existence, and thus, its operational capacity and institutional effectiveness remain limited. The average mean scores for operationalization (M ≈ 2.24) contrast the high ratings for integration potential (M ≈ 4.21–4.58), which indicates a gap between institutional intent and implementation. The LAPSSET is therefore viewed as a potential unifying infrastructural initiative, not only for East Africa, but also for the greater Horn of Africa. These views concur with the African Unions’ (AUs) Agenda 2063 aspiration and goal of an integrated Africa through world class transnational infrastructure.

Influence of Regional Coordination Mechanism on Economic Security Stabilization

A linear regression analysis was conducted to assess the effect of regional coordination mechanisms (RCM) within the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative on the economic security stabilization of the Horn of Africa. The model was statistically significant (F = 89.775, p < 0.000) with R² = 0.717, indicating that RCM and other predictors together explained 71.7% of the variance in economic security stabilization (Researcher, 2025).

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of Estimate
1	0.847	0.717	0.701	0.383

Table 3: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	39.615	3	13.205	89.775	0.000
Residual	15.625	44	0.355		
Total	55.240	47			

Table 4: Coefficients (Regional Coordination Mechanism)

Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
RCM	0.476	0.078	0.447	6.091	0.000

The results indicate that a one-unit increase in RCM is associated with a 0.476-unit increase in economic security stabilization. The standardized coefficient ($\beta = 0.447$) shows that RCM has the strongest influence among the predictors. This demonstrates the critical role of intergovernmental coordination, joint implementation, and communication mechanisms in enhancing regional economic stability under the LAPSSET initiative (Researcher, 2025).

6.0 DISCUSSIONS

The regional coordination mechanisms of the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative demonstrated the most significant influence on economic security stabilization in the Horn of Africa. Results depicted that a 1-unit increase in the LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism, may lead to a 0.476 unit (or 47.6%) rise in stabilizing the regional economy of the Horn of Africa, with ($p = 0.000$). This is a clear demand for coordinated planning, harmonized policies and co-operation between states, in-order to maximize the benefits of the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative.

These findings are consistent with analyses by the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA, 2023) and the World Bank (2024), which emphasized that the success of transnational infrastructure projects heavily depends on effective regional coordination. Well-structured coordination mechanisms reduce duplication of efforts, improve resource allocation, and enhance the predictability of economic outcomes. Similarly, studies by the Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD, 2022) highlighted that institutional and policy alignment among member states is a key determinant of the success of regional initiatives. Similarly, the findings of this study agree with IGAD (2022) studies, where it was observed that institutional and policy coordination of member states mostly determines the success of regional initiatives. The powerful effect of the LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism, demonstrated the need for cooperation of IGAD countries towards the achievement of the economic stabilization, which the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative aspires to deliver.

Although coordination is recognized globally for its positive influence, this study has presented context-related challenges. The lack of coordinated actions by the LAPSSET cooperating states has made it harder to implement decisions. Overall, an effective regional coordination mechanism for the LAPSSET is essential for achieving economic stabilization in the Horn of Africa.

7.0 CONCLUSION

This study assessed three indicators of the regional coordination mechanism of the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative, and how they influenced the economic security stabilization of the Horn of Africa. These indicators were; existence and operationalization of the LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism, stakeholder engagement and community inclusion in the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative, and regional integration and economic interdependence through the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative.

This study concluded that the regional coordination mechanism of the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative is a significant potential driver in bolstering the economic security stabilization of the Horn of Africa, having specifically observed that: the regional coordination mechanism of the LAPSSET infrastructural is yet to be drafted and jointly ratified by the current LAPSSET tripartite states (of Kenya, South Sudan and Ethiopia); the regional coordination mechanism of the LAPSSET is not operational, and thus, it does not enjoy committed governance support from the tripartite core; local communities are moderately engaged in the initiation and planning phases of LAPSSET projects; a LAPSSET regional coordination body jointly established by Kenya, Ethiopia, and South Sudan to manage the joint initiatives does not exist; and that a LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism has potentials for ensuring equitable access to integration benefits among affected communities in the Horn of Africa region, and thus, fostering collaboration between state and non-state actors.

Despite these gaps, the analysis demonstrates that an effective LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism has substantial potential to enhance economic security stabilization. Quantitative results

revealed that a one-unit improvement in the operationalization of the LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism could increase regional economic stabilization by 0.476 units ($p < 0.000$), confirming its statistical and practical significance. These findings underscore the necessity of establishing and operationalizing a functional LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism in-order to adequately deliver the economic stabilization objectives of the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative.

8.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

Recommendations for Practice

To enhance the effectiveness of the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative, this study recommended for the strengthening of the LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism as a central practice priority. Regional agencies, such as the Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD), should work closely with the tripartite governments of Kenya, Ethiopia, and South Sudan to harmonize trade, transport, and cross-border infrastructure policies. This collaboration would enhance connectivity, reduce trade barriers, and facilitate efficient utilization of strategic trade routes.

It is imperative that the LAPSSET tripartite states draft, ratify, and operationalize a joint regional coordination mechanism. Such a mechanism would formally reaffirm the commitment of the three states, ensure meaningful engagement of affected communities—including displaced and cross-border populations—in oversight and compensation committees, and promote community ownership of the initiative. Furthermore, the LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism should: facilitate the establishment of a LAPSSET supranational coordination body to oversee the joint governance, transparency, and accountability in decision-making and implementation of the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative; and also be dynamic enough to accommodate other willing states in the Horn of Africa (like Uganda, who earlier expressed interest in joining the LAPSSET initiative during its inception years), and thus, bolstered economic interdependence across the Horn of Africa.

Recommendations for Policy

In the foregoing research findings, the researcher proposed the following policy recommendations. First, the LAPSSET cooperating governments and regional policymakers should clearly establish regulatory frameworks which will guide the strategic re-conceptualization and implementation of an expanded LAPSSET mandate across the cooperating states in the Horn of Africa. These policies should mandate inclusive planning processes which consider governance, environmental and socio-economic impacts of the initiative, aimed at fostering regional integration and equitable distribution of integration benefits.

Secondly, the contracting parties to the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative should develop economic policies which safeguard investments, resource mobilization, employment and trade. Such policies have the potential to bolster regional growth and also attract investor confidence into the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative. Third, policies must strengthen regional coordination and governance mechanisms. Formal agreements, harmonized regulations, and joint decision-making mechanisms amongst the cooperating states should be institutionalized in-order to bolster seamless implementation of the LAPSSET infrastructural initiative, and thus, increase community acceptance of the LAPSSET initiative, and promote economic interdependence in the Horn of Africa. Additionally, these policies should encourage meaningful community participation, in-order to ensure that the LAPSSET initiative addresses community priorities and needs.

Fourthly, considering that current freedom of transit in the Horn of Africa is neither absolute nor guaranteed (Onditi, 2020), the researcher recommends that cooperating states of the Horn of Africa should establish a common transit policy, in-order to address the current problems of access to seaports and maritime transport by the three landlocked developing countries – Uganda, South Sudan, and Ethiopia - in the Horn of Africa. In the same breath, the cooperating states in the Horn of Africa should also establish joint resource mobilization policies, which should be dynamic

enough to attract south-south cooperation's and triangular cooperation's - like the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) - in funding regional infrastructure, both in the transit and landlocked developing countries, and thus, strategically addressing the problem of geography in landlocked developing countries in the Horn of Africa.

REFERENCES

- Adar, K. G. (2011). *Regional integration and peacebuilding in East Africa: The role of shared infrastructure*. African Journal of Political Science, 16(2), 45–67.
- African Union Development Agency - New Partnership for Africa's Development (AUDA- NEPAD). 2022. *Communique: 7th PIDA Week*. Communique, Nairobi: African Union Development Agency - New Partnership for Africa's Development (AUDA-NEPAD).
- Mtuku K Agade, and Halakhe A.B. n.d. (2019) "Rapid Assessment of the Institutional Architecture for Conflict Mitigation. A World Bank Group for Isiolo County, Kenya."
- Babbie, E. (2016). *The practice of social research* (14th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- Balbaa, M., Ahmed, S., & El-Hefny, M. (2023). Trans-Africa highway network: Impacts on regional trade and economic growth. *Journal of Transport and Development*, 19(1), 88–104.
- Braddon, M. (2012). Economic interdependence and conflict mitigation in Africa. *Journal of Peacebuilding and Development*, 7(3), 21–37.
- Braddon, Derrek. 2012. "Economic Interdependence and Conflict in the Horn of Africa." *The Role of Economic Interdependence in the Origins and Resolution of Conflict* 307-312.
- Browne, Adrian J. 2015. LAPSSET, The history and politics of an eastern African megaproject. The Rift Valley Institute 26 St Luke's Mews, London w11 1dF, United Kingdom.
- Chen, L., & Yao, H. (2023). Validity assessment in social research: Content, face, and construct measures. *Research Methods Journal*, 12(2), 101–115.
- Christian, P., Dlamini, T., & Ngugi, J. (2022). Regionalism in the 21st century: Security, political, and economic perspectives. *African Affairs*, 121(484), 235–256.
- Corral, Vijay Pillai and Miguel de. 2022. "Tackling fragility and promoting integration in the Horn of Africa through 'development diplomacy'." 1-5.
- Ethier, W. J. (1998). Regional integration and cooperation: Theory and evidence. *International Economics Review*, 39(2), 311–337.
- Fekade Terefe, Mulugeta Tesfaye. 2023. Good Governance Africa: Militarization of the Horn of Africa and what this means for regional security. October 9. Accessed February 7, 2025. <https://gga.org/militarisation-of-the-horn-of-africa-and-what-this-means-for-regional-security/>
- Gillham, Bill. 2008. "Developing a Questionnaire; Real World Research." *Research Gate*. January. Accessed February 10, 2025. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271524663_Developing_a_Questionnaire_Real_World_Research.

- Harris, L., & Green, P. (2022). Reliability and Cronbach's alpha in applied social research. *Journal of Applied Statistics*, 49(5), 1201–1218.
- HoAI Communique. (2024). *Horn of Africa Initiative: Regional corridor development and cooperation*. Horn of Africa Initiative Secretariat.
- Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD). n.d. *IGAD Economic Cooperation & Regional Integration*. Accessed February 24, 2025. <https://igad.int/economic-cooperation/>.
- Joseph S. Nye. 1968. *International Regionalism*. Boston, Massachusetts, United States: Little Brown.
- Kamau, J., & Owusu, K. (2021). Enhancing instrument validity in social science research. *African Journal of Research Methods*, 7(1), 56–70.
- Kombo, D. K., & Orodho, J. A. (2002). *Research methods*. Nairobi: Kenyatta University Institute of Open Learning.
- LAPSSET Corridor Development Authority (LCDA). (2016). *Brief on LAPSSET Corridor Project*. Government of Kenya.
- LAPSSET Corridor Development Authority (LCDA). 2024. *LAPSSET Corridor Development Authority (LCDA) Reports: Strategic Plan (2023-2027)*. January 31. Accessed February 7, 2025. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/18plceLYtvd43eVxSBGA1ltggJy6Su-tC/view>.
- Mingshu Wang, Ben Derudder, Charles Kunaka, Xingjian Liu. 2022. Regional integration in the Horn of Africa through the lens of inter-city connectivity.
- Schimmelfennig, Frank. 2018. "Regional Integration Theory." 1-46.
- Shakela Naz, Wu Yeyan and Liu Zhe and Keyao Ren and Yu Wenjie. 2022. "China-Pakistani economic corridor project bring the international trade, healthcare, self-efficacy, and social performance facility to Gilgit city, Pakistan."
- Silvester Kasuku. 2016. *Brief on LAPSSET Corridor Project*. Institutional, Nairobi: LAPSSET Corridor Development Authority.
- Sisay Asefa. 2003. *The Horn of Africa: Background, Scope And Regional Initiatives*. Analysis Report, Addis Ababa: Addis Tribune.
- Söderbaum, Fredrik. 2011. "Theories of Regionalism." 1-24.
- Stewart, F. (2008). Infrastructure, social cohesion, and conflict prevention. *World Development*, 36(2), 278–293.
- Thacker, S. C., Kaufman, D., & Koehler, P. (2018). Infrastructure development and conflict reduction in fragile states. *Global Development Review*, 5(3), 115–132.
- UN Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA). (2023). *Infrastructure and economic transformation in Africa: Regional perspectives*. Addis Ababa: UNECA.
- World Bank. (2024). *Transnational infrastructure and regional integration: Lessons from Africa*. Washington, DC: World Bank.

Table 1: Descriptive Results for Regional Coordination Mechanism of the LAPSSET Infrastructural Initiative

Statements	5 (SA)	4 (A)	3 (N)	2 (D)	1 (SD)	M	STD
Existence and Operationalization of Regional Coordination Mechanisms							
The LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism is in existence and was ratified by Kenya, Ethiopia, and South Sudan.	0 (0.0%)	7(14.6%)	15(31.3%)	23(47.9%)	3(6.3%)	2.29	0.94
The ratified LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism is operational and enjoys committed governance support.	0 (0.0%)	7(14.6%)	13(27.1%)	24(50.0%)	4(8.3%)	2.19	0.96
A regional coordination body jointly established by Kenya, Ethiopia, and South Sudan exists to manage the LAPSSET joint initiatives.	0 (0.0%)	7(14.6%)	14(29.2%)	24(50.0%)	3(6.3%)	2.23	0.93
Stakeholder Engagement & Community Inclusion							
Local communities are meaningfully involved in the initiation and planning of LAPSSET projects, and thus, reducing grievances and enhancing social harmony.	19(39.6%)	7(14.6%)	7 (14.6%)	15(31.3%)	0(0.0%)	3.77	1.13
A LAPSSET regional coordination mechanism has potentials for ensuring equitable access to Economic integration benefits among affected communities in the Horn of Africa region.	18(37.5%)	24(50.0%)	6 (12.5%)	0 (0.0%)	0(0.0%)	4.25	0.66
A LAPSSET coordination mechanism has potentials for fostering collaboration between governments, private sector, and civil society organizations in the Horn of Africa region.	28(58.3%)	20(41.7%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0(0.0%)	4.58	0.50
Regional Integration & Economic Interdependence							
A LAPSSET coordination mechanism has potentials for strengthening political and economic ties among cooperating states in the Horn of Africa region, especially by harmonizing the; disjointed transport and transit infrastructures, existing trade barriers and slow decision making amongst cooperating states.	30(62.5)	15(31.3%)	3(6.3%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	4.56	0.59
The LAPSSET coordination mechanism should be dynamic enough to accommodate other cooperating states (Uganda, Somalia, Djibouti, Sudan, and Eritrea) in the Horn of Africa region.	15(31.3%)	30(62.5%)	3 (6.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0(0.0%)	4.25	0.57
The inclusive LAPSSET coordination mechanism should receive governance support from regional institutions such as IGAD (Economic cooperation and Regional Integration Department) and Horn of Africa Initiative (HoAI). Thus, increased investor confidence in the LAPSSET Initiative.	13(27.1%)	32(66.7%)	3 (6.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0(0.0%)	4.21	0.54

Source: Researcher (2025)